

Part of
Data Management Plan for the TiMe3D Project: Multiscale
Time-Dependent Mechanical Properties of 3D Printed
Polymer Structures

Description
3D sample models

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CAD models of 3D samples for testing: (1) dog-bone shaped samples ISO527; (2) tubular samples for torsion and biaxial creep tests; (3) bar shape samples.

Researchers

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Description

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Models for the printing of samples for testing.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Other

CAD models

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

others

STL

1.1.4 Expected size of the data - give expected size and choose unit of measurement

KB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Yes, we have considered re-using some of the existing data.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

scientists

3D printer users

engineers

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers - DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

General Information

Relevance to the ISO Standard

Technical Specifications

Design Details

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

Yes

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Olga Bulderberga (orcid:0000-0001-8889-6451)

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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